

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Worksheet 2.1

The Competency Map

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A competency map offers a structured way to identify, align, and manage the diverse skills required across the full lifecycle of DestinE-based service development. In a context where technical, scientific, operational, and business expertise must converge, it provides an essential foundation for ensuring that services are technically robust, usable, relevant, and sustainable. By clarifying the roles and contributions of all involved stakeholders, the competency map strengthens coordination, reduces project risks, and supports the design of coherent co-design relationships.

This document introduces a comprehensive competency framework covering the key phases involved in transforming raw data into valuable services, from data provision and modelling to service design, delivery, and use. It helps teams diagnose their internal strengths, identify critical gaps, and determine where collaboration or capacity-building is needed. When used collectively, it supports project teams in designing balanced partnerships and allocating tasks strategically, ensuring that the project benefits from the right expertise at the right moment. The competency map also plays a central role in structuring co-design activities. By making explicit the competencies that must be aligned between partners and those that must be matched with user capabilities, it provides a clear basis for framing workshop objectives and organising effective collaboration.

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1. Introduction to the competency map

In the rapidly evolving field of Earth Observation (EO), the development of data-based services is becoming increasingly complex. Projects in this field often require a blend of technical, scientific, operational, and business-related competencies. They require not only cutting-edge technology and domain knowledge, but also a structured approach to project planning and execution. Critically, missing or underdeveloped competencies at any stage can lead to project failure or poor adoption. Typically, a technically sound service may fail if it lacks user engagement, doesn't meet real-world needs or doesn't address legal or ethical concerns. Without a clear mapping of these competencies, it becomes difficult to ensure that the right skills are available at the right time in the project.

The use of a competency map is an effective strategy for defining and aligning the various skills required throughout the lifecycle of a service, from conception to delivery and adoption. Another key reason to adopt a competency map in EO service development also lies in the diversity of expertise involved. EO projects typically involve collaboration across a wide range of stakeholders, including data providers, technology developers, public institutions, private companies, and end-users, each contributing distinct skills and perspectives. A competency map facilitates this collaboration by making the required skillsets explicit, thereby clarifying roles and responsibilities. It enables project managers to identify who contributes to what, and where external partners may be needed to fill gaps.

This document outlines a comprehensive competency framework essential for developing impact-oriented EO data services. The framework addresses five key phases: Data Provision, Data Leverage, Data Modeling, Service Design, and Service Delivery & Use. Each phase encompasses technical, scientific, business, operational, and collaborative competencies that are vital to the creation of scalable, relevant, and sustainable services. This framework aims to ease collaboration among diverse actors, mitigate risks by ensuring all necessary competencies are accounted for, and to support clearer project planning. In the high-stakes environment of EO-based service development, this structured approach can make the difference between success and failure.

1.1. Objectives of the competency map

The development of services based on Earth Observation (EO) and climate data requires a wide range of expertise, spanning technical, scientific, operational, and business domains. To support this complexity, a Competency Map has been designed with three main objectives in mind.

1. First, the **competency map aims to provide a common reference framework** for identifying and organizing the key competencies required to develop and deliver EO- and climate-based services. By clarifying what knowledge, skills, and roles are needed across the service lifecycle, the map helps structure the development process and ensures that no critical area is overlooked. It serves as a shared vocabulary for all actors involved in EO projects, from data analysts to business developers.
2. Second, in a diagnostic perspective, the **competency map enables service providers to assess the skills currently available within their team and to identify missing competencies that could hinder the success of their project.** This self-assessment capability is particularly valuable for organizations seeking to build internal capacity or to complement the project team. In particular, it helps identify the need for collaboration with partners in the implementation of a specific project and structure their co-design relationships by clarifying their mutual needs, respective roles, and the specific points around which they need to collaborate. Thereby, it is a key starting point for 'designing the co-'. It supports better resource planning, targeted training efforts, and informed recruitment strategies.

3. Third, **the competency map facilitates effective collaboration between complementary actors in a project.** By making each stakeholder’s competencies clear, the map encourages transparency and mutual understanding. It also helps teams design an efficient working model by distributing tasks according to who is best equipped to handle them. This ensures smoother workflows, reduces redundancy, and maximizes the use of available expertise.

Importantly, thinking in terms of competencies rather than fixed roles or structures allows teams to remain flexible. Rather than forcing a one-size-fits-all model of collaboration across all projects, this approach encourages teams to adapt their project setup based on the specific profiles and competencies of the actors involved—leading to more responsive and efficient collaborations. Thereby, the Competency Map is a strategic tool to structure projects, guide skill development, and foster successful multi-actor collaboration in the EO and climate data ecosystem.

2. Structure of the competency map

Consistent with the specific challenges raised by the development of services based on DestinE, the competency map is structured along two dimensions. The first dimension relates to the different types of competencies involved in the development of services based on DestinE data (2.1). The second dimension relates to the different steps in the process of transforming raw data into valuable user-centric services, based on the Data-Information-Value framework (2.2). Based on these two dimensions, a generic competency map is provided, identifying the specific competencies required at each step for each type of competencies (2.3).

2.1. Different types of competencies

Figure 1. The different types of competencies

2.1.1. Technical competencies

Technical competencies encompass the hands-on, operational skills required to design, develop, and manage data-driven services. These include expertise in data preprocessing, algorithm development, software engineering, and infrastructure management, particularly in

cloud-based environments. Professionals with strong technical skills can build scalable and robust services that transform raw EO and Climate data into actionable insights.

2.1.2. Scientific competencies

Scientific competencies involve a deep understanding of the physical processes, data characteristics, and theoretical foundations that underpin EO data. These skills ensure that data is interpreted correctly and meaningfully within its domain of application –e.g. climate science, agriculture, oceanography, or another field. This type of competence is crucial for maintaining the accuracy and relevance of EO products and analyses.

2.1.3. Business competencies

Business competencies are essential for translating EO capabilities into viable products and services. They cover areas such as strategic planning, market analysis, business model development, user engagement, and partnership building. Individuals with business acumen help bridge the gap between technical innovation and market demand, ensuring that EO solutions are commercially sustainable and aligned with real-world needs.

2.1.4. Operational competencies

Operational competencies refer to the skills needed to implement and operationalize EO services in everyday contexts. They refer to the specific competencies of users in their precise area of expertise (e.g. Managing nature in town, planning city infrastructures, etc.). They also include competencies related to the identification of potential users and use case in their daily operational context, their ability to envision the integration of a new service in their daily tools and workflow, etc. This knowledge and competencies related to the concrete use context of the service are critical to ensure data-based services are usable, impactful and respond effectively to user requirements and operational constraints.

2.1.5. Collaborative competencies

Collaborative competencies are critical for fostering collaboration and alignment across diverse stakeholders: technical teams, scientists, business leaders, and end-users. These skills involve communication, negotiation, interdisciplinary understanding, and the ability to mediate between different perspectives. By connecting silos and building shared understanding, boundary-spanning professionals facilitate the successful adoption and scaling of EO services.

2.2. The steps in the process of transforming raw data into valuable services

Based on the Data-Information-Value framework (the key framework used to perform co-design diagnosis, see *Worksheet 2*, key steps in the chain of transformation from raw data to valuable services were defined. These steps serve as a baseline for structuring the competency map, associating with each of them the main competencies required on each type. These steps are briefly described hereafter.

Figure 2. The different steps in the transformation of raw data into services

2.2.1. Data provision & support

This phase focuses on setting up and managing the data infrastructure required to access and process the data required to perform the targeted service, including DestinE data and potentially complementary data external to DestinE. Key competencies include mastery of e.g. cloud and data lake architecture, deployment infrastructure, and spatial database governance. Business competencies could also be required to secure relationships with data providers and infrastructure solution providers. Collaborative skills, such as cross-domain communication and stakeholder alignment, are essential to ensure smooth coordination among technical teams, data providers, and end users.

2.2.2. Data leverage

The **Data leverage** step involves maximizing the value extracted from Earth Observation (EO) data by transforming raw inputs into meaningful, actionable insights. Key activities include data acquisition from multiple sources (e.g., satellites, sensors), preprocessing and cleaning, integrating datasets for enriched context, and applying analytics or machine learning techniques to uncover patterns or trends. This step also involves curating data to meet user-specific needs, developing scalable processing pipelines, and ensuring compliance with data governance and interoperability standards. The goal is to generate high-quality, relevant information products that support decision-making, service delivery, and innovation across various sectors and user communities.

2.2.3. Data modeling

The **Data modeling** stage involves developing mathematical or statistical models based on Earth observation data to describe, predict, or classify phenomena. Key activities include selecting relevant variables, choosing suitable modelling approaches (empirical, physical, or AI-based), training and validating models using historical data, and evaluating their accuracy and performance. This step also includes model calibration, parameter tuning, and adaptation to specific use cases. The goal is to turn raw data into actionable insights through structured, interpretable outputs. These models form the core of many downstream applications, supporting decision-making and enabling reliable, consistent interpretation of complex environmental or geospatial data.

2.2.4. Service design

The **Service design** step focuses on transforming data models and user needs into operational Earth observation services. Key activities include defining service specifications, user interfaces, and delivery mechanisms. This involves close collaboration with stakeholders to ensure the service addresses real-world problems effectively. Designers prototype workflows, choose the right technologies for deployment, and ensure scalability, accessibility, and usability. Attention is also given to data formats, update frequency, and integration with

existing systems. The aim is to create a user-centric, robust, and sustainable service that delivers clear value, meets technical and functional requirements, and is ready for operational implementation.

2.2.5. Service delivery

The **Service delivery and support** step ensures that the services are reliably deployed, maintained, and accessible to users. Key activities include integrating the service within the users' technical infrastructure as well as daily work practices. It requires user onboarding, training, and providing clear documentation or tutorials. User support systems should be established to monitor the service use and performance, address technical issues, gather feedback, and provide guidance. Regular updates and maintenance should ensure data accuracy, system stability, and responsiveness to evolving user needs. Performance metrics can be tracked to assess impact and identify improvement areas. Documentation, training materials, and communication channels should also be developed to enhance user experience and engagement, ensuring long-term value and service sustainability.

2.2.6. Service use

The **Service use** step focuses on ensuring that end-users can effectively access, interpret, and concretely use the service to meet their specific needs. Key activities include from the user side includes setting up concrete decision process based on the service outcomes as well as complementing the service outcomes with complementary data to perform consistent analysis and interpretation of the relevant phenomena. Feedback mechanisms are implemented to gather user insights and measure satisfaction. Communication campaigns or stakeholder engagement strategies may be used to increase awareness and adoption within the user's organization. Usage analytics are monitored to understand how the service is being used and to identify any usability issues. The goal is to maximize the service's value, ensure ease of use, and encourage integration into user workflows and decision-making, which requires maintaining some form of ongoing relationship.

2.3. Competencies inventory

Based on the different types of competencies involved in designing DestinE-based services, and the steps structuring the process of transformation from raw data to useful service, an inventory of the competencies required to develop a useful service is proposed. It associates with each step, the set of competencies required by type (see Figure 3). This inventory stands as a competency map that should support service providers in developing new services based on DestinE

The competencies listed in this inventory aim at being generic and expected to be relevant to any domain (water, atmosphere, energy, land, etc.) targeted by the service, its types, use, and users. However, depending on the domain targeted by the service under design, these generic competencies can be detailed and lead to more contextual inventory. For instance, on the technical side, the types of protocol, coding language, or standards to master can be detailed further depending on the specific practices in a given domain.

This inventory should serve as a reference example to assess the competencies required for a given project, the missing competencies, and thereby elaborating a strategy for team training, collaboration and other forms of reliance on external competencies.

Figure 3. The competency inventory

3. How to use the competency map?

The competency map is a valuable strategic tool for building efficient, sustainable, and high-impact user-centered services. Using this competency map can significantly improve decision-making, optimize team and project structures, and strengthen collaborative paths.

Given that the competency map explicitly builds on the different dimensions covered by the DIV framework (see 2.2), it should be used as a complement to the diagnosis based on the DIV framework. The DIV framework allows for assessing the state of the service from a technical and usage perspective. The competency map allows for diagnosing the capacity of the stakeholders involved in the project to perform the necessary activities to deliver a viable service. This competency-based diagnosis therefore provides complementary and dynamic insight to the diagnosis based on the DIV framework.

This complementary perspective is particularly useful in projects that involve multiple stakeholders in the development of a service, such as a service provider working with technical or commercial partners. In this case, it should be used to help the partners organize their collaboration. When a project is led by a single entity, using the competency should be used to assess whether it possesses all the skills required to develop a sustainable commercial service or, conversely, to identify the competencies it lacks and for which it may need to engage with a scientific, technical, or commercial partner.

Overall, this competency map can be used to support effective co-design relationships following three key steps as described below (see figure 4): 1) Individual diagnosis; 2) Collective, project-level diagnosis; 3) Definition of the co-design process.

Figure 4. Three complementary uses of the competency map

3.1. Step 1 – Individual self-diagnosis of competencies

The first step in the use of the competency map for co-design is the individual diagnosis of the competencies of each team or stakeholder involved in the project. Typically, such a self-assessment should be performed during the framing or launch of a project by the stakeholder that will take part in¹.

¹Please note that it can also be performed on an ad hoc basis to plan strategic team development and learning paths.

The interest of internal diagnosis based on the competency map

Understanding the level of expertise of each stakeholder in each area of the competency map is a key foundation to launch the development of a service and structure an effective co-design journey. Whether the stakeholders are startups, research laboratories, government agencies, or mature EO companies, they should be able to define clearly where they stand in terms of competencies and what unique value they can bring to the project. The competency map should help them to clarify their current position within the chain of competencies.

Some typical outcomes of such self-assessment for the stakeholders can include:

- Identifying areas of strength to capitalize on;
- Highlight gaps that may require training or recruitment;
- Inform personal and organizational development plans;
- Prepare funding applications or partnership proposals clearly demonstrating competencies.

Typical process for internal diagnosis based on the competency map

The self-assessment based on the competency map should be performed during an internal workshop for each stakeholder gathering all the relevant people that will be involved in the project.

The typical steps to perform the self-assessment are the following:

- 1) Review the map's categories, to understand the key objectives and content of each step and the type of competencies required
- 2) For each dimension of the competency map specify each competency that are required given the specific domain you are working on (e.g. energy, water, land, etc.)
- 3) For each competency, rate your current level of expertise. This can be done using a quantitative scale in the table template (e.g., 0 = very low expertise, 1 = partly mastered, 2 = fully mastered) or using colors within the graphical template (e.g. Red = very poor expertise; orange = medium expertise; Green = very high expertise).
- 4) Based on your rating, identify which competency you should internalize or improve, which are out of your scope, and which can be accessed through partners. On this basis, a consistent positioning of the team within the project can be envisioned (and potentially any plans for training, hiring and/or collaboration can be formulated).

This first self-assessment supports an initial individual diagnosis, which should be updated regularly, but stands as a robust foundation for the second step.

3.2. Step 2 – Collective diagnosis of the project needs in terms of competencies

The second step in the use of the competency map for co-design relates to the collective diagnosis of the project's needs and gaps in terms of competencies. It explicitly deals with the overall structuring of a consistent co-design journey for the project.

The interest of the collective diagnosis based on the competency map

When working on the development of a service based on DestinE, it is essential to understand how the needed competencies are distributed, missing, or overlapping. The success of a project often hinges not only on individual competencies but on how the project team as a whole (often constituted by different complementary partners) covers the entire set of required competencies. Redundancies and gaps can lead to inefficiencies, delays, or poor-quality outputs. Typically:

- When not clearly identified, **missing competencies** can result in delays or failure. In contrast, an early identification of the missing competencies can help design training plans, onboard talents or seek for partnerships.
- **Overlapping competencies**, when not clearly identified and managed, can lead to ambiguities regarding the distribution of tasks or even tensions between the partners when they have conflicting understanding of their own positioning within the project. On the contrary, when carefully managed, such overlapping can stand a foundation for great complementarities and synergies between partners.
- Even when the entire set of competencies is gathered for a given project, a **poor distribution of tasks** among the team members or partners can lead to critical issues arising over the course of the project because of poor resource allocation.

A clear collective diagnosis of the project's needs in terms of competency should help address these risks by:

- A clear identification of the gaps and overlaps in terms of competencies;
- A clarification on the structure of the project and how task distribution can best leverage existing skills;
- A clear plan to fill in the missing competencies (e.g. through the search for new partners with specific competencies, training, etc.)
- A clear definition of the co-design needs between the partners and/or with the users, leading to a clear co-design journey

Typical process for the collective diagnosis of project needs in terms of competencies

This diagnosis is particularly valuable during project design or kickoff phases, but also useful at midpoints or evaluation stages. It should be performed collectively with each stakeholder engaged in the project during a collective workshop organized by the project leader to ensure alignment and clarify the expectation of each partner.

To be effective it should build on the individual self-assessment performed individually by the partners during the step 1. Accordingly, the typical steps in performing such a collective diagnosis are the following:

- 1) Before the collective workshop, the project leader gathers the self-assessment of each partner and merge them into one collective competency map for the project
- 2) The partners can then work together on the collective diagnosis during a collective workshop where:
 - Each partner briefly shares the results of its own self-diagnosis and its expectations in terms of positioning and role within the project
 - The project leader shares the merged diagnosis
 - The partners collectively identify the **core competencies** that are well covered, the **missing competencies** that no one possesses, or that are underdeveloped, and the **overlapping competencies** where multiple stakeholders may be doing the same thing.
 - Based on this collective diagnosis, the partners can start to structure an action plan to distribute tasks, fill the competency gaps and define a relevant structure of co-design workshops to ensure the various competencies stay aligned throughout the project
- 3) Following the collective workshop, the partners can refine this action plan, approve it collectively, and continuously update the competency map as a monitoring tool.

3.3. Step 3 – Framing the co-design workshops

The third step in the use of the competency map for co-design relates to the organization of the co-design workshops themselves either with potential users or with potential partners. In both cases, it should be used as a tool to frame the co-design workshop and as a support to structure and perform the workshop itself.

The interest of the competency map for framing the co-design workshops

For workshops with potential partners, the competency map should be used to clarify the scope of the collaboration and to focus co-design workshop on issues related to the alignment of specific competencies between the partners. In case of overlapping competences, the competency map can also help to clarify the respective position of the partners through the following outcomes:

- A clearer scope for the collaboration and potential synergies
- A clear task partitioning between the partners
- A clear identification of the specific issues on which the partners have collaborate

For workshops with users, the competency map can be used as a framework to clarify the scope of user competencies related to EO and climate data. Especially, it can help to assess whether they possess the competencies required to use the targeted service. Thereby, it helps to foster service adoption by designing a service that match user competencies and/or to plan training and support material accordingly. In this case, the use of the competency map should focus the following outcomes:

- A clear identification of the users' operational competencies and their competencies related to the use of the targeted service
- Clearer specification of the requirements to support usability and user adoption
- A better understanding of the needs for user training and support

Typical process for using the competency map in the framing of co-design workshops

Using the competency map for framing co-design workshops with partners and users is particularly relevant when preparing the co-design workshops. When used during preliminary exchanges and workshop preparation, it allows to clearly delineate the scope of the working relationship, what to focus on during the workshop and how to interact during the workshop.

Typically, the competency map can be used to spot critical areas where co-design should be used to align complementary competencies as to focus the workshop on the related issues. It can also be used explicitly during the workshop as a template to support interactions between service providers and partners or users.

Accordingly, the typical steps in using the competency map to frame co-design workshop are the following:

- 1) When preparing the workshop, the service provider should identify the specific areas of the competency map that should be addressed during the workshop (eg., because of competency overlap, missing competencies, etc.) and clearly define the associated co-design challenges to consider.
- 2) The service provider should identify relevant stakeholders to address these co-design challenges and engage with them to plan and frame the workshops.
- 3) Accordingly, a consistent workshop agenda can be built, supporting a step-by-step exploration of the potential scope and path for collaboration
- 4) During the workshop, the competency map can be explicitly used as a template to support discussion between the co-designers and to explicitly navigate the challenges addressed during the workshop.
- 5) After the workshop, the competency map can be used as a template to synthesize the outcomes of the workshop and the decisions that were agreed between the partners.

4. Conclusion

The Competency Map is a strategic enabler for building sustainable and impactful services within the Destination Earth ecosystem. By systematically identifying the competencies required across all stages of the service lifecycle, it reduces the risks of project failure due to overlooked gaps or poorly aligned expertise.

More than a static inventory, it functions as a living, collaborative framework that evolves with the project, guiding both internal team development and cross-organizational partnerships. Its strength lies in making roles and competencies transparent, thereby enhancing trust, efficiency, and shared ownership among diverse actors—whether they are data providers, technology developers, policymakers, or end-users. Used effectively, the Competency Map not only clarifies assignments but also structures the roles enabling the collaboration to take place. It ensures that the services are designed and delivered with the right balance of scientific rigor, technical robustness, business viability, and user relevance, ultimately accelerating adoption and maximizing societal impact.

Whether it is used for internal team diagnosis, or cross-organizational coordination, it brings clarity and coherence to multidisciplinary projects including scientists, technical developers, business developers, policy makers, and end-users. This is particularly crucial in the EO sector, where data complexity, technical innovation, and user-centered service design must converge. The thoughtful use of this competency map makes convergence more efficient, intentional, and impactful. To get the best outcomes from this tool, a couple of best practices should be kept in mind:

- A competency map supports agile management processes for smarter planning, clearer communication, and stronger collaboration with users and partners throughout the journey of service development. After a first competency assessment, it should be updated regularly to keep track of the team's evolution within the project.
- The competency map is a coordination tool, supporting alignment within and across teams, and clarifying complex interactions. The visual map should be used to clarify the positioning of each contributor to the project and their spaces for collaboration. Typically, it can be filled collectively with the members of a team and/or with external partners to clarify how each partner can contribute.
- The competency map supports a strategic approach to skills management. It supports the identification of the competency gaps that should be filled and helps to elaborate strategies to fill such gaps. The map can support key decisions on internalization versus externalization leading to onboarding new team members or engaging with new partners.

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